

Research for Impact in Digital Innovation

Proceedings of the 2nd RIDI Workshop

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Preface

Topics like Digital Transformation and Business Model Innovation are currently driving initiatives in industry; not only to introduce new technologies but also to gain significant business benefits. Hence, technology is not just seen as a means on its own but as one factor among others. Each digitally innovative project needs to incorporate the context of an organisation (market, customer segments) as well as its organisation and staff members. Challenges during such an endeavour are manifold. As a result, there is also an increased need in practice for more explicit guidance in terms of lessons learned, methods, approaches, principles, and design concepts.

Developing, and operationalizing, such explicit guidance entails demand-driven research and education, requiring synergies between applied research and practice. It also sparks a need for effective research methods that balance real world needs and contexts with scientific rigour.

Hence, a platform for individuals contributing to the development of explicit guidance for digital innovation by using research methods is required. Such a platform should bring together practitioners and academics, including researchers within the context of technical and applied sciences. The platform fosters exchange by discussing success stories and experiences from the field together with methodological approaches. It, furthermore, represents a trigger for shaping a research agenda together with corresponding methods in order to enable research in practice.

In line with this, the second European workshop on Research for Impact in Digital Innovation (RIDI 2024) aimed to bring together practitioners and researchers who are working in the area of digital innovation. It was conducted in Utrecht (NL) on April 11 and 12, 2024. Two invited keynote speakers as well as eight presentations sparked ideas that were discussed during a workshop session in the afternoon of the second day of the event.

The eight presentations were selected based on extended abstract that have been submitted and then reviewed by the organisation committee. The proceedings at hand bundles these eight abstracts in order to document the topics being discussed.

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ChatGPT Boosting Demands for Ethical Considerations

Becoming a better professional by evaluating ethical considerations

Theo Theunissen¹

Abstract:

IT Professionals consider ethicists relevant to the IT department. However, they are unfamiliar with the competencies, tasks, responsibilities, and authorities involved. Data privacy and algorithm transparency need to be implemented with the upcoming AI Act. A transdisciplinary approach is required with IT professionals, domain experts, data scientists, policymakers, and legal experts. Furthermore, the competence of architects and designers must be extended to accomplish both ethical and data science competencies. The layout of neural networks, model selection, data preprocessing, hyperparameter optimization, training, and optimization on development must be followed by process optimization, pipelines, and CI/CD for MLOps, a kind of DevOps for machine learning. Finally, values typically in the ethics domain contribute to becoming a better professional. For example, bias in deep learning is not so much a technical concept as an ethical value; taking bias into account results in a better-trained application. Green IT is another value that fits the United Nations' sustainability development goals. We present that a lack of explanation on the imbalance of privacy and transparency risks losing customers' trust. Incorporating ethical values makes the IT professional a better one.

Keywords: Ethics, IT

1 Introduction

With the introduction of Generative AI tools such as ChatGPT by OpenAI² in November 2022, Artificial Intelligence (AI), and specifically Large Language Models (LLMs) has gained a boost in attention in science, industry, and education³. Among many boosts, it is also pushing demands for ethical considerations. This leads to a surge from industry and education on how one can become a better professional by evaluating ethical considerations.

In a recent workshop for about 60 information professionals in the Netherlands on a case about ChatGPT in higher education Tlili u. a. 2023, we did the following observations⁴.

The first observation is based on workshop data, presented in Table 1. In the first round, everyone could mention a role that they considered relevant in this case. There were a total of 20 mentioned roles. Please note the high position of ethicists and the absence of an

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2 <http://openai.com>

3 Compare Google Trends for categories like <https://trends.google.com/trends/explore?cat=12&date=2017-01-01%202024-01-02&q=large%20language%20model&hl=en>

4 Organized by the Royal Society for Information Professionals (KNVI), held at November 23, 2024 at the Koninklijke Bibliotheek at The Hague

architect or designer. In the second round, participants had to vote for a role to elaborate on in smaller teams. All teams were productive in defining tasks, responsibilities, goals and motivations, fears and frustrations, tasks and activities, needs, and custom demands, except the group that discussed ethicists, who had an almost empty poster. This group had difficulty defining values, standards, rules, and regulations for a code of conduct, had difficulty positioning the role of an ethicist, and had a span of control for them.

The second observation concerns the need for more architects and designers with the introduction of ChatGPT in the organization. Typical tasks and responsibilities for an architect are to reason about the system, identify context, containers and components, interfaces with external systems, and prototyping. With the introduction of LLM, this role has also expanded to be a big data and pre-processing data architect, model architect, cloud architect, and prompt designer, and requires education in AI, Machine Learning (ML), and data science.

The third observation, which emerged in the plenary discussion afterward, is that production tools differ from education tools. Tools for production are, for example, coding assistants for software developers or image generators for graphic designers. Tools for education should help students better understand topics by evaluating results, generating self-tests, or giving a head start on the structure of a report. Of course, instructors must teach students that ChatGPT functions as a stochastic parrot and that the best results are sub-optimal. Furthermore, the AI Act *Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council Laying down Harmonised Rules on Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and Amending Certain Union Legislative Acts 2020* considers education a high risk because of using AI to determine access to training institutions or assess students' results required to admission training institutes.

The fourth observation in the plenary discussion was intrinsic values related to a discipline. Information professionals prioritize privacy and transparency, while lawyers and legislators emphasize justice and fairness. In healthcare and medicine, values revolve around the autonomy of the body, avoiding maleficence, and striving for beneficence for the patient. Communication strives for dignity, equality, and inclusion.

The last observations lead to an investigation for becoming a better professional by taking ethical considerations into account. A first example considers a Database Administrator (DBA) how to become a better professional by taking privacy into consideration. A second example considers developers and system engineers who become better by taking CO₂ into consideration. A third example considers trainers in a neural network who take bias into account and thereby become better neural network trainers.

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Appendix

ID	Team	Role	Voted
R1	1	Student	25
R2	2	Lecturer	22
R3	3	Ethicist	11
R4		Examiner	
R5	4	Information specialist	7
R6	5	Jurist	7
R7	6	Privacy Officer (PO), Chief Information Security Officer (CISO)	6
R8		Researcher	6
R9		Education Inspectorate	3
R10		Receptionist	2
R11		Supporting Staff	2
R12		Librarian	1
R13		Purchase (licenses)	1
R14		Administration	0
R15		Students Dean	0
R16		Executive Board	0
R17		Internship Supervisor	0
R18		IT Department	0
R19		Data Steward	0
R20		Facilities Management	0
R21		Management	0

Tab. 1: List of a survey of roles and votes for discussing roles.

Transforming with technology

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1 Extended Abstract

1.1 Introduction

Technological innovations follow each other in rapid succession. This article provides organizations with insight into important factors which will help to embrace these technological innovations and achieve a successful transformation of the entire organization. These technological innovations do not only impact the design of an organization, they will impact its business model and personnel structure as well.

1.2 Framework

In the upper funnel of the Smart UP Ecosystem model (Figure 1), the different pioneer phases of transformations (interest, desire and action phase) are described. These phases provide insight into focus areas to promote a successful disruptive transformation. This is done from the following perspectives:

- Technology
- Business
- Human

Fig. 1: Pioneering Phases for Digital Transformation [Gi20]

1.3 Data collection

Narrative discussions were held with twelve organizations that had implemented smart technology and consequently experienced disruptive transformation. The learning experiences from these interactions have been incorporated into case studies, and the patterns within these cases have been analyzed. The areas Technology, Human, and Business Organizations were the main focus.

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1.4 Results

After analyzing the case studies, the following factors were found to be conducive to transformations:

1. The network of the organization, both internal and external, is crucial in the ability to transform. From the very first beginning of the transformation, the so-called interest phase, a network of (public) organizations is required, as this will help in finding smart technology which fits the purpose of the organization.
2. Important is that the internal and the external network possess the right competencies for digital transformation: the current external and internal knowledge and skills are often not sufficient and need to be developed.
3. To ensure that the organization has access to state-of-the-art knowledge about smart technology, the pioneers should be able to do experiments in corporation with other (public) organizations and have time to develop themselves. Day-to-day business should not get in the way. Change capacity, room for experimentation, management skills, long-term goals with a concrete innovation budget and strategy are required to facilitate experiments.
4. The choice of the smart technology is related to the state of the IT architecture of the organization. Mature IT-architecture helps the digital transformation.

This shows that collaboration in a balanced network of stakeholders is essential. In addition, it also requires a certain maturity from the organization, so that time, resources and infrastructure are available in sufficient quantities.

The results have been incorporated in the model below (Table 1) and are linked to the areas Human, Business and Technology and the phasing of Interest, Desire and Action. Based on this model, an organization can position itself in relation to the phase in which the innovation is located. This then provides insight into the next steps to be taken in the areas of Human, Business and Technology.

Interest	Desire	Action	
I am aware of the value that the use of smart technology adds to my business (which information problems it solves for end users)	I considered whether the impact of the smart technology could be organized for all aspects of the business model (Business case/change capacity)	I know what steps I need to take to steer the development of each part of the new digital business model	Business
I am aware of which external and internal network I need to actively use to take steps with regard to digital transformation.	I have considered whether I can achieve the digital transformation with my own people, need new people or need to collaborate with people outside the organization.	I know what steps I need to take to set up a powerful learning and working environment which guides the learning process and development of the organization and enables its digital transformation.	Human
I am constantly monitoring new developments and trends around smart technology that may be relevant to my organization (technology radar).	I have considered whether, based on the current IT foundation, there are possibilities with regard to the use of smart technology (functional adjustments can be estimated)	I know what steps I need to take to set up systems to solve the information problems.	Technology

Tab.1: Results

1.5 Future research

Follow-up research can provide more insight into the interfaces where Business, Human and Technology come together in transformation processes. These interfaces include the following aspects:

- Adjustability: focused on the possibilities of human adaptations to technology and vice versa.
- Actionability: focused on people's willingness to adapt to a changing business model. Investments in the learning capacity of employees are often necessary when the business model changes.
- Accessibility: to what extent is the technology accessible to the business and is the business ready in terms of organizational maturity for the technology.

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Teaching Research for Impact in Post-graduate Information Systems Education

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1 Motivation

Post-graduate education in the Information Systems discipline aims to prepare students for their later career in industry or academia. Both areas require that students are ready for applying their skills and knowledge in order to solve issues in the respective environment. This refers to applying existing knowledge but also to perform typical research tasks and find a solution that yet might not have been discovered. Even though this sounds academic, such a skill is also one of the predominant expectations on students with a master's degree when being hired by a company. In contrast to common bachelor programs, companies expect an emphasis on methodological competencies in post-graduate teaching.

Classical teaching methods often prioritize the transmission of knowledge, sometimes at the expense of nurturing individual research skills and problem-solving techniques. The rapid emergence of new technologies and methods in information systems poses challenges for both educational institutions and companies, the prospective users of these evolving technologies. There is a pressing need for universities to adjust their curricula to equip students with the skills necessary for seamlessly integrating these technologies into their professional lives. These skills are crucial for enabling companies to comprehend the limitations and advantages of emerging technologies, facilitating fact-based decision-making. However, the swift pace at which these advancements occur poses a significant challenge for universities to adapt their curricula accordingly.

Hence, a more anticipatory teaching is required which enables students to adapt to new situations and be ready to develop solutions [St08]. The paper at hand describes a project-based module that aims to support students with developing skills so that they will be enabled and empowered to solve real-world problems.

2 Background: Action Learning and Impact

For decades, the concept of action learning (AL) is presented and discussed in higher education [Re82]. AL aims to support students with learning in small groups and being

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guided by mentors (rather than being *taught*) while developing a solution for a real-world case or problem [Zu18]. Students are tasked with developing a concept or a solution for a given problem, all while being mentored or coached. The role of a mentor or coach is not to dictate the path to a solution but to assist the group in their journey, fostering a self-direct learning approach. A crucial aspect of the learning journey involves students in identifying relevant knowledge required for the solution.

Serrat recommends that AL should "focus on real-life, practice-related problems that are open-ended in nature and do not have a right or wrong answer"[Se17]. A University can only simulate such a setting when defining a case study to be worked on during AL. Consequently, practitioners with real-world cases should be involved so that students experience are within a similar, but well protected, situation as in real life. This active engagement also serves the purpose of bridging the gap between classroom activities and the tangible impact that the outcomes can have on a company.

The Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences (Frankfurt UAS) offers a dedicated project module as part of the curriculum of the master's program in Wirtschaftsinformatik (Business Information Systems). It is accounted with 10 ECTS so that a workload of 300 hours is expected. Students form teams of three to five members who will have to work on a common project. In order to put an emphasis on the impact of the projects, challenges are usually provided by external companies. One or more representatives from the company act in the role of the customer who will be the beneficiary of the result. The customer does not define a specific result but rather expresses his requirements on a real-world challenge to be solved. The role of the customer, together with the mentor, also encompasses to provide feedback on their perception of intermediate results without giving advice how the corresponding team continue working. Students are expected to work independently and perform research tasks whenever they are required.

3 Example Project

Such a project has been conducted from October 20, 2023 until end of February 2024 together with FINIUS GmbH in Eschborn (near Frankfurt, Germany). A team of three students has specifically chosen this project, which aimed at developing a prototype for a business capability map generator. FINIUS consultants, as part of their assignments, are developing business capability maps for customers, based on best practices and existing reference models. Consultants are experienced Business Architects but such a task remains time consuming and error prone, even though typical maps follow common rules and principles. At present, there is no tool support available to assist in creating a business capability map from the ground up tailored to a specific industry or customer. The prototype is supposed to be used by consultants in the future or, at least, should serve as a proof-of-concept for such an endeavour.

The student team was free to choose the tools and frameworks for implementation. There was a suggestion to use Generative AI as FINIUS also aims to understand the potential of this technology for their future business. The project was also restricted to one industry, public transportation, in order to have a realistic scope. Based on these requirements, the team had to catch up the necessary skills and perform research on similar projects and publications, like machine learning in enterprise modelling [SBB23] or prompt engineering [Li23]. Together, one consultant from FINIUS and the responsible Professor from the Frankfurt UAS, helped to balance research and development in order to achieve a result that has an impact for consultants.

Even though the prototype has been developed for a specific industry, it already indicates promising results for the consultancy. The required time for generating a first draft business capability map will be reduced drastically. It still needs to be edited by an experienced consultant (adding company specifics, rephrasing with respect to individual business terminology) but the overall time was reduced from a couple of days or weeks to a few hours. The prototype also avoids typical issues of manually created maps. The amount of "hidden or undiscovered Capabilities" will be reduced as the capability mining will be fed with documents from all departments.

As the result was perceived as a *booster* for the work of a consultant, students recognised the relevance of the impact such a research prototype. Instead of just implementing a tool based on technology, they needed to evaluate the output in a business environment. They also learned more about the context in which the tools will have to be applied and needed to adjust their implementation iteratively. This makes the difference between developing a tool and solving a real problem.

4 Summary

Students need to learn how to solve problems on their own (or in small teams) in order to be successful in their future work life. AL can help with training respective skills and gaining experience. However, a classical university setting bears the danger of just performing some artificial case study which does not link to a benefit for a company. The student projects in the Business Information Systems master's program at the Frankfurt UAS are offered together with industry partners which provide real-world challenges to the teams. The experience, so far, is as follows: AL combined with a realistic task fosters a sustainable learning approach and helps students with training problem-solving skills, i.e. performing research for impact.

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Enhance Return on Modelling Effort by Generating Software in InformationGrid and Mendix

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Abstract: With Simplified Modelling Platform we are able to model in various notations and transform between these notations. We have used the DEMO notation to create four software generation scenarios where we target platforms like InformationGrid and Mendix. The successful generation of application and application frameworks gives modelling a better return on modelling effort and can help business to adopt more modelling effort.

Keywords: enterprise engineering, DEMO, modelling tools, software generation

1 Extended Abstract

Small and medium sized businesses seldom use the modelling practice for drawing up their organisation. The return on modelling effort is simply too low. The more IT is going to be included in those businesses, the more cluttered it becomes. In the end, some drawings are made but the step towards modelling is often too big. In consultancy the first advice in modelling is often setting up enterprise architecture where simple process and data modelling would be a sufficient step. This step is sometimes skipped, and then never revisited again, because the complexity is low enough to understand the processes without a model. We experience that one of the ways to create more value in modelling is to optimise the connection between modelling and the operationalisation of the models to generate software.

For the creation of the relevant models, we have employed our Simplified modelling platform[Mu22] which supports modelling in multiple notations[MMB23]. As for the the operationalisation of the models we have identified two target platforms, namely InformationGrid and Mendix.

InformationGrid is time-based platform that uses domain driven design. It is a cloud based real-time interpretation platform that provides API on every created data aspect. Because it is time based with a current state it can act as a data platform and data warehouse at the same time.

Mendix is a application platform that is based around a relational database and micro flows that execute functionality.

The combination of the modelling capabilities of Simplified and the operational capabilities of InformationGrid is a seamless integration where the domain design is the linking pin. The recognised synergies between these two products have led to using the Simplified modelling platform for creation the domain model and transformation of this domain model into an InformationGrid model that can be executed.

We have started research on the transformation of models in a master “Towards a round-trip transformation between DEMO and VISI”. We have also supported a master on Simplified on

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“BPMN-SD transformation” as well as started two PhD studies with the working titles “Describing the transformation language for graph-based models” and “Describing transformation rules for the evolvability of models” The current state of transformation is such that it supports single tree recognition and transformation within the model graph.

Currently, we have identified four viable scenarios for model-based operationalisation.

The first scenario is the data warehouse staging generation with CRUD where we can support the back-end application integration within an organisation. With the input of an API JSON structure we can generate a DEMO Entity Type. This Entity Type is then transformed into a set of InformationGrid types of which the Aggregate Type is the main structure. This structure is composed of non-SQL data structures and commands that manipulate the contents via events. In the transformation we add the supporting commands: Create, Update, and Delete.

The second scenario is the application generation with CRUD support The input of the transformation is a Fact Diagram (Entity Types with attributes) in the DEMO notation. With the algorithm of deciding the core entity and the nested child entity we create the Aggregate Type of InformationGrid. The Aggregate Types will support the commands: Create, Update, and Delete on every core and child entity.

The third scenario is the application and process generation where we can generate two dimensions of the organisation. Again, the input of the transformation is a DEMO notation, but this time with fact, construction, and process model. By having these three aspect models, we can transform such models into an IG configuration where commands correspond with the defined transaction kinds and transactions steps from the DEMO method. This, in turn, would make the front-end UI following defined business processes instead of only CRUD commands as in the second scenario.

The last scenario is the application and process core generation into Mendix. A Mendix overlay, ACACIA, has been built, accepting the DEMO transaction kinds and fact kinds transformed into their intermediate format.[Kr23]. Just like scenario three, the input of the transformation is a DEMO notation with fact, construction, and process model. We transform this model into the API requirements as dictated by ACACIA.

At the moment, we have the first and fourth scenario operational in the laboratory environment and are looking for a first customer. We are also working on the other solutions where we want to incorporate the the PhD transformation results in these scenarios.

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I-Doctorate: Public-public partnership between government and higher education

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Keywords: I-Doctorate, National Government, Public- Public Partnership, Higher Education

1 Introduction

To maximize the capabilities of digital technologies, public institutions must undergo a comprehensive reconsideration of the institutional and organizational components inherent in the conventional governmental framework, commonly denoted as the digital government transformation in the scientific literature [Ta21], [DFS22] and practice-based literature [De21]. This expedition addresses various internal and external challenges through a compelling digital transformation process in the public sector [Al22]. In the Netherlands, an initiative was launched to examine and tackle these challenges with PhD-researchers and higher education institutions: I-Doctorate.

I-Doctorate aims to connect the network of universities to national governmental organizations, fostering continuous development, sharing, and implementation of knowledge on digital matters within the government. Engaging through PhD research ensures the establishment of long-term trajectories and collaborations. This ultimately results in state-of-the-art innovations that are being developed for the government and an increase in highly skilled employees. However, the ultimate goal is to provide good services to citizens and businesses, strengthen education through real-life case histories, and ultimately ensure a digitally strong Netherlands. As far as we know this is one of the few dual (academic-governmental) PhD research possibilities in the world.

2 The concept

In concept, the governmental organisation employs the PhD candidate for an extended period, dedicating three days to practical work and two days to academic research. By engaging with a doctoral candidate, an organization secures top-tier talent for an extended duration, establishing a lasting connection between the organization and

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academia. This ensures ongoing awareness of the latest advancements and possibilities, facilitating the ability to take truly sustainable steps in addressing digitization challenges [Rij24].

A dual system is the starting point of every research project and revolves around a digital challenge. The challenge is untangled and tackled by academic research with support from an extensive knowledge network consisting of academics and civil servants. This knowledge network consists of people, but also of thorough knowledge of the issues itself. The question is what knowledge or expertise does a governmental organization need for a solution and how can that knowledge, expertise, and talent provide a solution? The idea is to work with so-called 'knowledge portfolios' mapping digital government issues on the themes of information governance, data, and artificial intelligence, as well as cybersecurity or cyber resilience and quantum technology. These issues are linked with the expertise and knowledge of academic research partners to enable knowledge exchange and development. An important part of this work is the 'translation' of governmental issues to academic knowledge and scientific insights to practical solutions.

3 A step-by-step approach

I-Doctorate offers organizations the opportunity to access top ICT talent and in-depth specialized knowledge to address complex digitalization challenges. This step-by-step approach outlines how governmental organizations can begin integrating PhD candidates into their activities.

3.1 Define the research question

Organizations seeking an innovative and independent approach to their digitalization challenges, or those needing structural contributions in terms of innovation, knowledge, and scientific research, can benefit from I-Doctorate. This program is particularly suited for those looking to address government-wide themes such as information management, cybersecurity, and other current issues. A PhD candidate conducting research within the organization can play a critical role in these areas.

3.2 Formulate the proposal

Your organization's core mission is to address key I-related challenges of today and the future, leveraging the latest technologies and their applications. However, the approach ("how?") may not always be clear. I-Doctorate assists in refining research topics and questions and in determining the research strategy.

3.3 Role of the I-Doctorate

I-Doctorate acts as a bridge between academic networks and government organizations. By fostering continuous knowledge sharing and development, your organization gains access to a substantial knowledge base. In collaboration with its partners, translating policy agendas and priorities into research proposals for PhD candidates, tailored to the digitalization needs. This makes research into critical I-themes an integral part of the activities and supports the implementation of innovative solutions. Additionally, I-Doctorate coordinate various knowledge questions to enhance collaboration within the government.

3.4 Implementation Steps

In collaboration with the I-Doctorate Program and academic experts, the organization's I-challenge is translated into research questions suitable for PhD-level investigation during a workshop. I-Doctorate assists organizations in concretizing research topics, formulating research questions, and developing a research approach. Your organization then drafts a job description and recruits a suitable PhD candidate, with our support through our network. Once a candidate is found, I-Doctorate assists with the contract and onboarding process. Your organization ensures the PhD candidate effectively integrates into your team.

3.5 Expected Results

By participating in the I-PhD Program, your organization gains immediate access to a PhD candidate who works three days a week within your organization and conducts research two days a week. This results in PhD-level research carried out by a talent who is also actively involved in your organization. You receive materials to share knowledge both online and offline. If the PhD candidate replaces an external consultant, not only is knowledge retained within your organization, but you also save costs. Additionally, the university network makes it easier to recruit interns and students for thesis research.

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Using Erasmus+ Projects to Create Impact

the Case of the European Software Skills Alliance

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Abstract: HU University of Applied Sciences Utrecht participated in an Erasmus+ project, involving over 20 organizations, that addressed the EU's ICT personnel shortage by creating the European Software Skills Alliance (ESSA). ESSA, a four-year initiative, aims to meet software skills demands through a comprehensive strategy and curricula. A mixed-method approach is followed to identify technical and soft skill needed across 12 EU countries. Resulting role profiles and training materials were developed and will be freely available post-2024, aiming for long-term impact in digital innovation.

Keywords: Erasmus+, ESSA, European Software Skills Alliance, Education and training development

1 Introduction

In this abstract we present an Erasmus+ project in which the HU University of Applied Sciences Utrecht is participating as an example on how such projects can combine scientific research with education and practice. The reason to start the project is the fact that the shortage for ICT personal in the EU is large and expected to increase. To ensure that training material is available for up- and reskilling a consortium of over 20 organizations (public and private) developed the European Software Skills Alliance (ESSA) proposal.

ESSA “is a four-year transnational project funded under the EU’s Erasmus+ programme. It ensures the skills needs of the rapidly evolving Software sector can be met — today and tomorrow. ESSA provides current and future software professionals, learning providers and organisations with software needs with the educational and training instruments they need to meet the demand for software skills in Europe. ESSA will develop a European Software Skills Strategy and learning programmes for Europe. It

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will address skill mismatches and shortages by analysing the sector in depth and delivering future-proof curricula and mobility solutions; tailored to the European software sector's reality and needs.”[ES21]

As part of the ESSA project a needs analyses is performed with the goal to understand which roles and competences in the software services sector are needed now and in the future in order to develop curricula that is better aligned to market demand. For this the following research question was formulated: *Which competence gaps do we need to bridge in order to meet the future need for sufficiently qualified personnel in the EU Software sector?*

A mixed method approach was used to map the current and future needs for competences in twelve different EU countries. The analyses showed that the demand for technical skills is changing and that a stronger focus on soft skills like communication and critical thinking is needed. Furthermore, the study found that educational institutes should integrate real assignments in collaboration with organizations in curricula.

Based on the needs analyses a paper was presented and published in the conference proceedings of the 36th Bled eConference [Mo23] (science). In the follow up of the project programme learning outcomes were developed for the following role profiles (junior) developer (EQF 5/6/7), DevOps (EQF 6/7), Solution Designer (EQF 6/7), and Test Specialist (EQF 4/5). Subsequently learning material was assembled and/or developed and piloted by both institutes of higher education and commercial training providers (practice). After the project is finished (end of 2024) all materials will be freely available to use by any party whom wishes to do so (possibility to realize longterm impact).

Following the presentation of the ESSA example during the RIDI workshop a discussion will be moderated with the aim to determine whether this type of project can be a good vehicle to realize impact in digital innovation, and if so, what aspects should be taken into account when developing and implementing these type of project proposals.

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Researching Online anti-Palestinian Racism in German Language in the Context of Staatsräson and Institutional Censorship

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Abstract: Online anti-Palestinian Racism in the context of a broader process of anti-Palestinian censorship practices in modern Germany, historically tied to a pro-Israel position, remains an understudied research area for Information Systems researchers. This paper addresses this by examining what kind of online hate speech can be considered online Anti-Palestinian Racism (APR) on Twitter in the German language. The findings are discussed in the context of Germany's Staatsräson ideology and diminishing academic freedom when it comes to Palestinian rights.

Keywords: anti-Palestinian Racism, online hate speech, Staatsräson, Germany, academic freedom.

1 Introduction

Research does not happen in a vacuum. We are influenced by what happens in the world, nearby and further. The October 7th attacks of Palestinian fighters from Gaza on Israeli targets have had massive implications on geopolitics and society, including Germany.

While Germany has the largest Palestinian diaspora in Europe, Palestine continues to be a contentious issue in higher education, particularly in Germany and in German-speaking academia [1, 2], or as Ayyash [3] states "*The 'Palestine Exception' is so pervasive on campuses in the United States, Canada, the United Kingdom, and Germany...*"

Germany's Staatsräson—its special relationship with and outward support for Israel is rooted in the "historical responsibility of Germany for the Shoah, including the security of Israel, as part of Germany's "*Staatsräson*" (reason for existence)." [4]. Against this context, advocacy for Palestinians' human rights is seen as suspicious. Several cases of institutional anti-Palestinian Racism and censorship have happened in Germany, from cancellation of speakers and firing of staff in academia, as well as outside in denying the right to protest, or cancellations of cultural events or McCarthyism in German media. The following table presents examples of academic and cultural stifling in Germany (Table 1). The data was collected by the European Legal Support Center (ELSC) and covers the period from 7 October 2023 until 31 January 2024 [5].

Refusal/Withdrawal of Use of Venue or Cancellation of Event	Smear Campaign	Loss of Employment or Suspension from Position	Threats to Academic Freedom	Disciplinary Investigation	(Attempted) Defunding
Venue providers refuse to allow Palestine related events or activities to take place on their premises; withdraw their consent to use the venue; an event is cancelled completely or the content is resisted.	Making inflammatory allegations against an individual, group or organisation on public or private platforms with the intention to tarnish their reputation and delegitimise their work.	Incidents in which individuals are dismissed from employment, suspended from their position, their nomination for an award withdrawn, or their qualification is cancelled because of their support for Palestinian rights.	Situations whereby the ability of scholars, researchers and academic faculty to freely pursue and disseminate information, research and ideas about Palestine and Israel are restricted	Formal complaints against individuals or groups on account of their activism or expression for Palestinian rights. These expressions could take the form of social media posts, speeches at protests, podcasts, literature or talks. The complaints involve unfounded allegations of antisemitism or harassment.	Pressure exerted on private and/or public donors to withdraw their financial support to civil society organisations or groups.
Example:	Example:	Example:	Example:	Example:	Example:
Events are permitted to go ahead by universities or public and private bodies but with severe restrictive caveats put in place such as the requirement of all speakers to acknowledge the IHRA definition of antisemitism.	A professor or artist is accused in the news of being anti-Semitic for supporting BDS or for publishing pro-Palestine posts on social media (case of anthropologist, Chassan Hage and Max Planck Institute)	Case of Palestinian novelist, Adania Shibli's award celebration cancellation.	A professor or student may not be allowed to book a room at their university for a meeting or event about Palestine with the explanation that it is "not neutral".	Unfounded allegations of racial harassment, discrimination or support for terrorism.	Hostile groups contacting an organisation's private donors alleging they are participating in antisemitic activity.

Table 1. Cultural and academic stifling in Germany. Source: European Legal Support Center (ELSC).

From my own experience –well before October 2023- the author faced some veiled (and unfounded) accusations of antisemitism from German academics when conducting a study on online anti-Palestinian Racism in the German-language Twitter-sphere. This experience and the observed 'Palestine Exception' sensitivity in Germany led to identifying the research gap for this paper.

Understanding cases of or denial of online anti-Palestinian Racism in the context of a broader process of anti-Palestinian censorship practices in modern Germany, historically tied to a pro-Israel position, remains an understudied research area for Information Systems researchers.

2 Objective(s)/Research Question(s)

Combined with the researcher's research interest in underprivileged groups who face under-representation online and decolonisation of the discourse regarding history and politics, the following research question (RQ) and discussion topic for RIDI 2024 is proposed:

RQ: What kind of online hate speech can be considered online Anti-Palestinian Racism (APR) on Twitter in the German language?

The objective is to identify online attacks, censorship and hate speech targeting pro-Palestine activists or Palestinians in the German Twitter-sphere using an AI-enabled platform. The hypothesis is that a culture of (offline) institutional anti-Palestinian Racism in Germany has a relation with online anti-Palestinian Racism.

Discussion topic for RIDI 2024: in the context of Germany's Staatsräson and institutional suppression of voices for Palestinian rights inside and outside academia, is **academic freedom** endangered? For example, is conducting research on anti-Palestinian Racism possible, such as discussing the identification of (online) anti-Palestinian Racism and the implications for AI-enabled detection and content moderation systems

- Academic freedom is recognised in the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and comprises freedom to research, teach, study, and academic expression. Conditions for ensuring academic freedom include institutional autonomy and self-governance, among other things [6].

A 2022 EU-commissioned study showed a very positive score for Germany, despite some worries about the "blurring of boundaries between the higher education and science system, politics, the private sector, and civil society", where the report mainly highlighted domestic populism and China's influence as issues of concern [7].

3 Related Concepts

The concept of hate speech has many legal and non-legal definitions and implications [8]. For this extended abstract we adopt the European Union's definition [9]: "*hate speech is defined in EU law as the public incitement to violence or hatred on the basis of certain characteristics, including race, colour, religion, descent and national or ethnic origin.*"

Anti-Palestinian Racism (APR) is a specific form of hate speech. In this hate speech, Palestinians are presented as 'terrorist', 'antisemitic', and 'undemocratic' [10]. Anti-Palestinian Racism targets Palestinians but also affects those who stand in solidarity with Palestinians (ibid). This form of Racism has not gotten much attention from most Western scholars and public discourse; even faces (self-) censorship in academic discourse about race and Racism and the exclusion of Palestinian academics [3]. For this research, the following definition suggested by ACLA [11] is adopted:

Anti-Palestinian Racism is a form of anti-Arab Racism that silences, excludes, erases, stereotypes, defames or dehumanizes Palestinians or their narratives. Anti-Palestinian Racism takes various forms including:

- *denying the Nakba [ed. ethnic cleansing since 1948] and justifying violence*

against Palestinians;

- *failing to acknowledge Palestinians as an Indigenous people with a collective identity, belonging and rights in relation to occupied and historic Palestine;*
- *erasing the human rights and equal dignity and worth of Palestinians;*
- *excluding or pressuring others to exclude Palestinian perspectives, Palestinians and their allies;*
- *defaming Palestinians and their allies with slander such as being inherently antisemitic, a terrorist threat/sympathizer or opposed to democratic values*

4 Method

4.1 Data collection tool

A tool developed for an EU-funded project was used for the first data collection phase. This tool provides a dashboard for multilingual and multiplatform online hate speech AI-enabled lexicon-based detection and monitoring.

For this initial data collection in this EU-funded project, the data was anonymised in the dashboard before being released to the researchers for analysis. This meant anonymisation of the names of persons, places, hyperlinks, usernames, ages, et cetera. However, the names of public figures (e.g., local politicians) are not anonymised, as they may provide helpful context about the hate messages.

4.2 Case selection

With this tool two cases were examined: 1) anti-Palestinian Racism and 2) misogynoir

For data collection on anti-Palestinian Racism in the German language a specific lexicon of anti-Palestinian racism keywords and phrases was manually created and used as training data for the AI-enabled system.

5 Results

Approximately 95K tweets were collected from September 2021 to February 2023. The manually created lexicon of typical anti-Palestinian Racism was revised multiple times to include newly identified terms, which helped to increase the data collection. This was done by identifying co-occurrence analysis of certain words with the already identified anti-Palestinian racism keywords.

According to the AI-enabled dashboard, only 2% of the collected messages were deemed very toxic, with a score >0.8 (on a scale from 0 to 1). We argue that forms of Racism such as anti-Palestinian Racism that are understudied may be under-reported or under-valued in toxicity, as often the people scoring the toxicity may not have a deep understanding of the offensiveness of certain words for an understudied marginalised group, such as Palestinians. For example, the term 'Pallywood' is offensive as it suggests that Palestinians are playing the victim and made up stories when they share testimonies of atrocities committed by the Israeli forces. This term is not part of the stand lexicon of hate speech in the AI-enabled platform and was manually added for this study to capture online anti-Palestinian Racism.

5.1 Emerging themes

By qualitatively analysing samples of the collected data, the following themes emerged:

- Pro-Palestinian rights activists face false accusations of holocaust denial or antisemitism (weaponising controversial IHRA description)
- Terror group fearmongering and accusations
- Denying Right To Resist Occupation (part of International rights) & BDS. Boycott, Divestment, Sanctions (BDS) is a Palestinian-led movement for freedom, justice and equality.
- Dehumanisation of Palestinians
- Denial of the existence of Palestine, Palestinian people or occurrence of ethnic cleansing of Palestinians ('Nakba')
- Intersection of islamophobia, online-gender based violence & other forms of discrimination with anti-Palestinian Racism

6 Themes of Anti-Palestinian Racism identified in the data

Three forms of 'racial gaslighting'; "a form of gaslighting designed by those with power to maintain the status quo over marginalised groups" (Abu-Laban and Bakan, 2022):

- A **denial** of the lived experience and reality of Palestinians, creating harm. For example, Nakba denial: refusing to acknowledge ethnic cleansing in 1948 and onwards in occupied Palestine
- **Gaslighting** directed at those with less power to maintain the status quo, supporting the colonial project of Israel and diverting attention from its oppressive character.

- Involves **blaming the victim**, typically by demonising/pathologising those who resist oppression.

Next to these three forms of gaslighting, we see the following, namely **weaponising** alleged antisemitism (particularly by applying the IHRA-working definition) for framing criticism of Israel as antisemitism or by **conflating** Israel [state] with Judaism [religion]. "The IHRA definition has been heavily implicated in the suppression of Israel-critical speech in recent years", Ruth Gould [12] argues. Germany has adopted this controversial definition, de facto silencing pro-Palestinian support and dissent against Israeli policies or atrocities [3]. A consequence of this may even be inflated of antisemitism figures, consequentially enhancing the 'blaming the victim' frame of Palestinians and Palestinian rights activists. This, however, lies outside of the scope of this study.

This study presents initial findings on anti-Palestinian Racism in the German language Twitter and suggests a related discussion topic on academic freedom.

6.1 Future work

A second phase of data collection on Twitter in German (focusing on Twiplomacy by German state officials and entities) and Dutch since October 7th, 2023, has started to compare and contrast the findings in different languages and socio-political geographies. This may be expanded with data collection in English from the United Kingdom.

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Digital twins to support the planning and control of discrete manufacturing processes

Gerlinde Oversluizen¹, Vincent Wiegel²,

Abstract: Demand customization leads to increasingly complex production planning and control (PPC), resulting in declining delivery reliability. Digital twinning is an emerging technology that can support PPC by improving the responsiveness of production systems. However, many production companies face challenges in implementing digital twins in value adding way due to unmet prerequisites and the absence of a standardized approach to digital twin (DT) modeling. This research aims to contribute to the development of generic DT modeling principles. To achieve this, we employ a combination of intervention-based and design science research methods.

Keywords: digital dwin, production planning and control, demand customization, research methodology, practice oriented research, design science research, business cases

1 Problem context and business question

Production Planning and Control (PPC) is becoming increasingly complex. The resulting execution delay is caused by several facts (See fig.1). On the one hand, this is caused by large volume fluctuations due to geopolitical circumstances and more customer-specific demand(2). On the other hand, production systems suffer from limitations(3) and lack of flow(4). As a result the production system responsiveness(6) is insufficient to absorb the effects of the mentioned external factors(2). Hence, production companies struggle with their throughput times(7) and delivery reliability(8).

To counteract above influences on the responsiveness, companies eliminate waste and uncertainties(4,5) and reduce the impact of limitations(3) using improvement principles such as Lean or Six Sigma. These principles help improve the flow(4). However, the increasing variations in external factors(2) make the management of internal limitations(3) more complex.

Timely planning adjustment, fed by (near-) real-time process data, is a strategy to further improve the responsiveness of the production system(6) [ZH21]. Digital twin technology (DT) helps to uncover and analyze real-time data. DTs support(9) the the PPC-organization, and thereby improve the responsiveness(6) [WA21].

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Figure 1: Influences on the responsiveness of discrete production systems

Based on these claims many companies start DT projects with high expectations. However, they turn out to be insufficiently able to use this new technology in a value adding manner. They encounter barriers like data validity and employee skills [CH21; GH22].

The following business question is deduced from the above formulated problem:

How do we (the companies) introduce digital twinning step by step into our production system, to support our complex production planning and control in a data-driven way, taking into account the limitations in the production system, with the aim to increase the responsiveness to variations in supply and demand, resulting in on-time delivery to our customers?

This business question is the focus of our research. Eight discrete production companies (from high variety low volume SMEs to high volume LE's in sheet metal, plastics and PCB production) participate in this research. They want to improve their production system responsiveness in a data-driven way.

2 Research approach

To introduce digital twins in production processes various process models are known [Sc20; TN21]. However, these process models do not give in-depth insights on DT-modeling, and relevant modeling principles. Fuller et al. [Fu20] note there is no standardized approach to DT-modeling, that cover all aspects of a digital twin from the

physical and virtual modelling to the data, connection and service parts of a digital twin. Concluding Fuller et al. [Fu20] state there is a need for a generic modelling principles for a complete digital twin.

This research aims to contribute to the generic DT-modelling principles for digital twins in PPC (the so called operation digital twin (ODT) [BA19]). In addition to Fuller et al. [Fu20] we hold the position that these principles not only concern the mentioned (internal) aspects of the digital twin but also the ODT-design in conjunction with the production process and the PPC-organization. To attain these principles, we use a combination of intervention based (IBR) [Ol19] and design science research (DSR) [VA16].

In small iterations the companies involved work step by step on the introduction of ODT-functionality. The experience and findings from these cases are input to derive generic modelling principles for ODTs. To bridge the gap between case-specific design and generic design in intervention and design science research, we use the guidelines proposed by Van Aken et al.[Va16]:

- a. Establish validity per case
- b. Derive generic ODT-modelling principles.
- c. Establish validity of the generic ODT-modelling principles

Next to contributing to the generic ODT-modelling principles this research aims to fortify and enrich the existing process models. During the ODT-introduction process employees from all levels are involved. They are supported to determine lessons learned per iteration and establish organizational next steps based on these lessons. This approach facilitates the learning process of companies and enables extension of the existing process models. General formatting

3 Contribution to RIDI2024

In our contribution to RIDI2024 we present:

1. A rich case of practice-oriented research in discrete production companies using a combination of intervention based (IBR) and design science research (DSR).
2. An application of the guidelines proposed by Van Aken et al. [Va16] in a viable, manageable but also justifiable way.
3. An approach to facilitate the knowledge creating and sharing process within companies helping them to work through the obstacles during introduction of digital twin functionality.

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Program

Thursday, April 11

- 10:00 Welcome by the organisers
- 10:30 Get together – sharing expectations
- 11:15 – Keynote
12:00 *Stijn Hoppenbrouwers*
- 13:00 ChatGPT Boosting Demands for Ethical Considerations
Theo Theunissen
- 13:30 – Transforming with technology
14:00 *Hubèrt Bijsterveld, Jeroen van den Hoogen, Yvonne Peterman and Mariëlle Seegers*
- 14:15 I-Doctorate: Public-Public Partnership between Government and Higher Education
Kees Teszelszky and Guido Ongena
- 14:45 Digital twins to support the planning and control of discrete manufacturing processes
Gerlinde Oversluizen and Vincent Wiegel
- 15:15 – Teaching Research for Impact in Post-graduate Information Systems Edu-
15:45 cation
Jürgen Jung and Pierre Wienke
- 16:00 Discussion and summary day 1
Erik Proper and Guido Ongena

Friday, April 12

- 9:00 – Keynote
10:00 *Erik Fledderus*
- 10:15 Enhance Return on Modelling Effort by Generating Software in Information-Grid and Mendix
Mark Mulder and Fiodor Bodnar
- 10:45 Researching Online anti-Palestinian Racism in German Language in the Context of Staatsräson and Institutional Censorship
Anand Sheombar
- 11:15 – Using Erasmus+ Projects to Create Impact – the Case of the European
11:45 Software Skills Alliance
Pascal Ravesteyn, Sabine Boesen-Mariani and Guido Ongena
- 13:00 – Workshop: Setting a Research Agenda for Impact
15:30 *moderated by Stijn Hoppenbrouwers and Pascal Ravesteijn*